

NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

RM 8

DELIVERABLE N° 28

MILESTONE N°

SPOKE 5 – Industry of Health and Silver Economy

Version history

No.	Date	Details	Author(s)
0.1			
0.2			
0.3			
0.4			

REPORTING PERIOD

Period covered: from [01/10/2022] to [30/04/2024]

The milestone n... and the deliverable n.28 ("Scientific paper on ActR-Fc-nLG3 efficacy in old mice"), in the framework of RM8, were due by They have been successfully reached by the expected time, as reported in the following image: indeed an epub version of the paper entitled "Synergistically Acting on Myostatin and Agrin Pathways Increases Neuromuscular Junction Stability and Endurance in Old Mice" has been published on the journal *Aging and Disease* (IF 7.4) in August 2023.

Original Article

Synergistically Acting on Myostatin and Agrin Pathways Increases Neuromuscular Junction Stability and Endurance in Old Mice

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[Received April 8, 2023; Revised July 11, 2023; Accepted July 13, 2023]

ABSTRACT: Sarcopenia is the primary cause of impaired motor performance in the elderly. The current prevailing approach to counteract such condition is increasing the muscle mass through inhibition of the myostatin system; however, this strategy only moderately improves muscular strength, not being able to sustain the innervation of the hypertrophic muscle per se, leading to a progressive worsening of motor performances. Thus, we proposed the administration of ActR-Fc-nLG3, a protein that combines the soluble activin receptor, a strong myostatin inhibitor, with the C-terminal agrin nLG3 domain. This compound has the potential of reinforcing neuro-muscular stability to the hypertrophic muscle. We previously demonstrated an enhancement of motor endurance and ACh receptor aggregation in young mice after ActR-Fc-nLG3 administration. Now we extended these observations by demonstrating that also in aged (2 years-old) mice, long-term administration of

Recently, on April 2024, the article has been re-indexed, because the Journal released the printed version, as shown below. However, although the publication year looks different now (2024), the DOI has remained the same (10.14336/AD.2023.0713-1).

Original Article

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